

Integrating a Zero-Trust Adaptive Security Framework in Edge based Federated Learning

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Abstract—Federated Learning (FL) allows multiple clients to collaboratively train a machine learning model without sharing their raw data, thus addressing privacy data concerns. The joint application of FL (Federated Learning) and MEC (Multi-Access Edge Computing) enables efficient utilization of computation and storage resources at the edge. By deploying the FL model at the edge, data are trained locally on the device or edge node, reducing latency, and facilitating real-time processing and decision-making, whilst also ensuring data privacy. However, the decentralized FL is subject to security and trust challenges, since MEC data may get poisoned. Therefore, ensuring the trustworthiness of clients is pivotal to ensure integrity and performance of FL models. This paper presents an adaptive Zero Trust framework which assumes no inherent trust in any client, is based on continuously verifying and validating the clients' behavior, to ensure that only reliable contributors (clients) are incorporated in the global model aggregation.

Index Terms—Zero Trust, Federated Learning, Mobile Edge Computing, privacy, machine learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

In this paper we aim to demonstrate an innovative approach designed to contribute to the privacy, integrity, and performance of Federated Learning (FL) systems by incorporating a trust evaluation mechanism [1].

Despite the considerable progress in FL and edge computing, there are still gaps [2] in existing knowledge that need to be addressed. Firstly, is the lack of comprehensive techniques for data verification and validation in FL that can address the challenges of data privacy and data quality in FL while maintaining scalability and feasibility [3]. And secondly, the limited understanding of the practical challenges of implementing FL and edge computing techniques in real-world settings, where data could be compromised [4],[5].

The proposed approach builds on the literature by introducing and implementing a trust-based FL framework that integrates Multi-Attribute Decision Making (MADM) techniques, with a primary emphasis on the

Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to an Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) method [6],[7]. TOPSIS, a widely adopted MADM technique, is employed to rank clients in the FL process based on multiple performance metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, and the Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve (AUC) [8]. These metrics are combined in a weighted scheme, that obtains a trust level allowing for the computation of trust scores that adapt to each client's evolving behavior over the training rounds.

The core of the methodology lies in the TOPSIS technique, which ranks clients by measuring their proximity to an ideal performance and their distance from an anti-ideal, or worst-case, performance. Each client's trust score is determined by calculating the Euclidean distance between the client's performance and the ideal solution, making TOPSIS an effective approach for handling the multi-dimensional nature of client evaluation in FL [10],[11]. This method ensures that clients closest to the ideal performance are ranked higher, while those further from it are assigned lower trust scores.

To strengthen the robustness of the model training process, the framework incorporates the proposed Adaptive Trust Score Scaling System Filtering (ATSSSF). ATSSSF applies a threshold based on the trust scores computed by TOPSIS, filtering out clients with low trust scores before aggregation. By adaptively adjusting the importance of various performance metrics and filtering unreliable clients, ATSSSF ensures that only clients with higher trustworthiness and who meet required threshold level are able to contribute to the global model, thus preserving model integrity and improving convergence speed. The framework is designed to mitigate the impact of unreliable or malicious clients by continuously evaluating trust levels, hence ensuring that only high-performing clients participate in the aggregation process.

II. PROPOSED FRAMEWORK DESIGN

The proposed framework builds on the Flower framework [9] (refer to Fig.1), that establishes a secure and efficient communication platform among decentralized devices. The architecture and deployment involve configuring tasks on both the MEC nodes and server. Each MEC node has a unique dataset, along with model, hyper-parameters, and training methods. Global computation oversees the entire learning process on the server without knowledge of individual client data. The data loader handles the loading and preprocessing of training data, including the intentional flipping of a portion of labels to simulate adversarial behaviour.

The ATSSSF applies this adaptive filtering mechanism, as illustrated in Figure. 2 ensuring that clients with trust scores below a predetermined threshold are excluded from the aggregation. The LSTM model

Fig. 1: Iterations - shows both none and label flipping

architecture is used for training, together with the averaging algorithm FedAvg. The trust scores are updated after each training round to reflect the latest client performance metrics. The client selection and omission process are managed by the central server, which filters out and omits clients with low trust scores to ensure that only reliable contributions are considered.

The ATSSSF mechanism illustrated in figure 2, integrated into the modified FL framework process, leverages MADM techniques, specifically TOPSIS, to evaluate and rank MEC nodes based on their performance

Fig. 2: FL custom component integration in the Flower Framework Process Showing Client Omission (ATSSSF).

metrics - accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, AUC-ROC are combined by applying a weighted scheme to calculate a trust score that reflects each client's reliability. The trust score is updated in real time, ensuring the FL process adapts to the MEC Node's performance fluctuations.

The TOPSIS method ranks clients based on their proximity to an ideal solution (best performance) and an anti-ideal solution (worst performance). The process starts with the formation of a decision matrix where client performance metrics are normalized for comparability. Weights are assigned to each metric based on their relevance, and the Euclidean distance from both the ideal and anti-ideal solutions is computed [12]. MEC Nodes are ranked according to their relative closeness to the ideal solution, and those with trust scores below a predefined threshold are omitted from the aggregation process. The TOPSIS method is integrated within the FL framework. Algorithm 1 illustrates the TOPSIS process, in how MEC Nodes performance metrics are fed into the decision matrix. This matrix serves as the basis for ranking clients. The metrics are first normalized to ensure comparability across different clients, and then weights are applied to prioritize certain metrics based on their importance to the current training round. Once normalized and weighted, the Euclidean distance of each client from both the ideal (best-case performance) and anti-ideal (worst-case performance) solution is calculated [12].

Algorithm 1. further illustrates how these rankings

are used to filter out untrustworthy clients before the global model aggregation takes place. Clients with low trust scores, derived from the TOPSIS process, are omitted from contributing to the final global model. The ATSSSF applies this adaptive filtering mechanism, ensuring that clients with trust scores below a predetermined threshold are excluded from the aggregation. This assists the FL framework to avoid incorporating

Algorithm 1 TOPSIS - Client Ranking in Federated Learning

- 1: **Input:** Performance metrics for N clients across m metrics: $\mathbf{M} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times m}$
- 2: **Output:** Ranked list of clients based on TOPSIS scores
- 3: **Step 1: Form the Performance Metrics Matrix**
- 4: Form matrix \mathbf{M} where each row i represents client i and each column j represents a performance metric:

$$\mathbf{M} = \begin{pmatrix} \text{Loss}_1 & \text{Accuracy}_1 & \text{AUC}_1 & \text{Precision}_1 & \text{Recall}_1 & \text{F1 Score}_1 & \text{Trust Score}_1 \\ \text{Loss}_2 & \text{Accuracy}_2 & \text{AUC}_2 & \text{Precision}_2 & \text{Recall}_2 & \text{F1 Score}_2 & \text{Trust Score}_2 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \text{Loss}_N & \text{Accuracy}_N & \text{AUC}_N & \text{Precision}_N & \text{Recall}_N & \text{F1 Score}_N & \text{Trust Score}_N \end{pmatrix}$$

- 5: **Step 2: Normalize the Performance Metrics**
- 6: **for** each metric j in 1 to m **do**
- 7: Calculate normalized value $x_{ij}^{\text{normalized}}$ for each client i using min-max normalization:

$$x_{ij}^{\text{normalized}} = \frac{x_{ij} - \min(x_j)}{\max(x_j) - \min(x_j)}$$

- 8: **end for**
- 9: **Step 3: Apply Weights to the Normalized Metrics (if applicable)**
- 10: Define a weight vector $\mathbf{w} = [w_1, w_2, \dots, w_m]$ where w_j is the weight for metric j
- 11: Form the weighted normalized matrix \mathbf{W} :

$$\mathbf{W} = \begin{pmatrix} w_1 \times \text{Loss}_1^{\text{normalized}} & w_2 \times \text{Accuracy}_1^{\text{normalized}} & \dots & w_m \times \text{Trust Score}_1^{\text{normalized}} \\ w_1 \times \text{Loss}_2^{\text{normalized}} & w_2 \times \text{Accuracy}_2^{\text{normalized}} & \dots & w_m \times \text{Trust Score}_2^{\text{normalized}} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ w_1 \times \text{Loss}_N^{\text{normalized}} & w_2 \times \text{Accuracy}_N^{\text{normalized}} & \dots & w_m \times \text{Trust Score}_N^{\text{normalized}} \end{pmatrix}$$

- 12: **Step 4: Prepare for TOPSIS Method**
 - 13: Use the weighted normalized matrix \mathbf{W} as input to the TOPSIS method:
 - 14:
 - 1) Compute the ideal best and worst solutions.
 - 2) Calculate the Euclidean distance of each client from the ideal best and worst solutions.
 - 3) Determine the relative closeness to the ideal solution for each client.
 - 4) Rank the clients based on their relative closeness scores.
 - 15: **Step 5: Return the ranked list of clients based on TOPSIS scores**
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poor-quality or malicious weights, thus maintaining model robustness, improving accuracy, and ensuring faster convergence. The adaptive nature ensures that trust scores are updated dynamically based on real-time performance data, allowing the system to adjust the set of MEC Nodes that contribute to the global

model in each training round.

III. DEMONSTRATION RESULTS

The experiment was carried out using the Flower Framework (Fig.1) harnessing the TOPSIS approach as given by Figure 2. The demonstration scenario constituted 10 MEC nodes over 5 iterative rounds, representing a typical distributed networking architecture. A mechanism to simulate the presence of adversarial clients or poisoned data is implemented through random label flipping. Each client is assigned a probability of being adversarial, and set at 0.5, meaning there is a 50% chance that any given client will behave maliciously. If a client is chosen to be adversarial, it will flip a portion of its training labels based on a specified probability ranging from 0.1 to 0.9. This label flipping distorts the training data, effectively "poisoning" the dataset. The proportion of labels to be flipped is determined by the FLIP_PERCENTAGE parameter, while the likelihood of a client engaging in this behavior is dictated by the FLIP_PROBABILITY parameter. This adversarial behavior is configured through environment variables in the Docker_Compose setup environment, ensuring that each client's behavior is probabilistically determined at runtime. By implementing this setup, the impact of poisoned data on the FL process has been studied and the robustness and resilience of the model training against such adversarial attacks has been evaluated.

The demonstration scenarios show the performance in the presence and absence of adversaries (label flipping), as given by Fig. 3. The evaluation Loss is

Fig. 3: Iterations - shows both none and label flipping

consistent across all clients at 0.3046, indicating that the average loss during the evaluation was stable. The Evaluation Accuracy was also consistent, showing an accuracy of 0.8409 for all clients. The AUC metric was approx. 0.9716 across all clients, suggesting a high probability to distinguish between positive and negative classes. The Precision was 0.7843 for all

clients, indicating a relatively high ratio of true positive identifications among all positive identifications. Moreover, the Recall is uniformly high at 0.9808, demonstrating strong capability to identify nearly all positive cases. The F1 Score balances precision and recall, providing a single metric that reflects both false positives and false negatives. The F1 is 0.8716, showing a balance between precision and recall, suggesting effective performance across all clients.

The ATSSSF Score varied slightly among clients, ranging from 0.8457 to 0.8514, demonstrating the model's ability to assess and maintain stable performance. Finally, the Trust Score varied among clients, with scores around 0.6509 to 0.6795, indicating moderate to high trust in the model's prediction capability during the evaluation. Overall, the model demonstrates strong and consistent performance across multiple evaluation metrics.

The performance evaluation with adversaries (Fig. 3 with label flipping) where we assume data flipping probability of 0.1 - 0.9, and a probability of a client being adversary of 0.5. In this context, the Evaluation Loss is 0.3589, suggests that the model's predictions are close to the actual values, indicating a good fit on the validation data. The Evaluation Accuracy is 84.08% indicating that the model correctly classifies about 84% of the instances. The AUC is high at 0.9555, indicating excellent model performance in distinguishing between the classes. It suggests that the model has a high true positive rate and a low false positive rate. The Precision is 0.7904, suggesting that when the model predicts an intrusion, it is correct about 79% of the time. The Recall is approx. 0.9673, indicating that the model captures about 97% of the actual intrusions. The F1 Score is given by 0.8699 that shows good performance. The ATSSSF average is 0.84, showing consistent performance across different clients. Finally, the Trust Score varied from 0.61 to 0.67, showing variability among clients, possibly indicating differences in data quality or model performance consistency.

The FL approach for the IDS (Intrusion Detection Systems) model shows robust and consistent performance across multiple clients, with high recall and AUC scores demonstrating its effectiveness in detecting intrusions, where a total of 3 out of the 10 clients were omitted before model aggregation.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper aims to demonstrate a novel trust evaluation framework for FL, incorporating Zero Trust principles to achieve privacy, security, and enhanced performance. The proposed implementation has shown to provide a robust, deployable, and scalable approach

to trust management in FL, by ensuring that only trustworthy clients contribute to model training. By adjusting the threshold for client inclusion based on their relative closeness to an ideal solution, the FL system maintains high model performance and security. The proposed framework has shown how to effectively evaluate client trustworthiness, dynamically adjust trust scores, and omit low-trust clients.

Future work aims to address scalability and convergence performance where we would expect to observe consistent adversary detection, and improved model accuracy, convergence speed, and robustness. Real-world applications include deploying in agnostic systems at the edge, i.e. in precision farming clusters, where we would expect to observe consistent adversary detection and improved model accuracy, convergence speed, and robustness.

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